

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #7

Decarbonisation of the heating sector in Lyngby

By Technical University of Denmark

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Executive Summary

Figure 34 - Decarbonisation of the heating sector: A multidimensional approach mixing centralised and decentralised heating systems in Lyngby Municipality, Denmark – Graphical Abstract

This case study explores technical, economic, and social aspects for the municipality of Lyngby to achieve 98% district heating access by 2030, figure 34. The case study concludes that transitioning to district heating requires better

stakeholder communication, integration with neighbouring systems, and attractive business models. Collaboration and strong political support are necessary for successful implementation.

Abstract

Denmark has set out its objective to achieve a 70% reduction in its greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to the 1990 level with the Climate Change Act of June 2020. This is the primary milestone before the country becomes a net-zero emitter in 2050. In the heating sector, the target is to reach full decarbonisation by 2035. Measures include expanding district heating networks.

However, there are also areas in Denmark where houses are too scattered for district heating, and individual households will have to consider other options for decarbonised heat. In this context, Danish municipalities such as Lyngby need to obtain a concrete assessment of the situation.

The district heating in Lyngby still relies on gas-fired facilities and many of the community's residents live scattered and far from the current network. Yet, the city aims to have 98% of district heating access by the end of 2030. That is a dramatic increase from 65% today. Lyngby is therefore looking for both centralised and decentralised solutions which can help them achieve the outcome at an affordable cost.

The problems to be addressed are technical, economical, and social, both at individual and district heating levels. The project focuses on different technical, social and economic aspects of achieving 98% coverage but also on sustainable solutions for the remaining 2%, which will not be connected to the main grid.

Introduction

Context and motivation:

Denmark has set out to achieve a 70% reduction in its greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to the 1990 level with the Climate Change Act of June 2020 (Ministry of Climate, 2020). This is the primary milestone before the country becomes a net-zero emitter in 2050. By 2021, Denmark had managed to reduce its emissions by 38%.

This represents a significant achievement, but it also stresses the difficulty ahead. Today, 96 of the 98 Danish municipalities have developed strategic energy planning to reduce their carbon emissions. In that respect, the government's recently published "Danmark kan mere II" (Denmark can more II) (Danish Government, 2022) stresses the urgency to accelerate gas independency in the current geopolitical context. Measures include expanding in priority the district heating networks and allocating more than DKK 3 billion to subsidise the replacement of oil and gas boilers. However, there are also areas in Denmark where houses are too scattered for deploying district heating, and individual households will have to consider other options for decarbonised heat.

In 2022, the Danish government explicitly established the responsibility of the municipalities to draw up plans for green heat in the currently gas-supplied areas and to guide

households' energy choices towards heat sources compliant with national policy. Therefore, municipalities need to obtain a concrete assessment of the situation. The municipality of Lyngby-Taarbæk (LTM) is an excellent example of the current constraints on the supply of carbon-neutral heat in Denmark. First, most of its district heating supply still relies on gas-fired facilities. Second, many of the community's residents live in homes supplied by individual natural gas boilers. LTM is therefore looking for both centralised and decentralised solutions which can help them achieve the outcome at an affordable cost for the inhabitants while ensuring social equity.

The problems to be addressed are technical, economical, and social, both at individual and district heating levels.

Which sources of heat can be found? What are the costs going to be? How many will accept the offer to connect to district heating? The 98% potential coverage may not necessarily mean that 98% in fact will use the heat from the district heating network.

Research gaps: Most residential energy consumption is today attributed to heat consumption – see Figure 35. This makes the decarbonisation of heat production critical to reaching our emission reduction targets.

Figure 35- Energy consumption in EU households (Eurostat, 2023).

The issue of access to heat is particularly intertwined with the development of cities (IRENA 2020, Arabzadeh et al. 2020). City and energy planners have a central role in steering the low-carbon transition at the local level with the decarbonisation policies, (Bloess et al. 2018, Heendeniya et al. 2020) in concert with energy companies and city stakeholders.

District heating is a clear path for decarbonising the heat sector in Denmark and achieving EU transition targets (Hast et al. 2018). District heating presents multiple technical solutions to produce heat. Additionally, the centralised nature of district heating embraces economies of scale, leading to lower heating costs for end-users. However, legal or geographical restrictions often stand in the way of building new DH, requiring users to adopt

individual decentralised heating sources such as heat pumps. DH is an energy capital-heavy infrastructure requiring long investment horizons. Unlike e.g. electricity grids, DH as a technology is subject to competition with other types of heat supply. Households have a wide range of individual heating types and fuels to select between. This introduces risk to DH systems, as investment certainty is key for the deployment. For the end-user, investment in a new heat source is a large expense that households may be unwilling or unable to make. Households are, however, often unaware of their heat sources' long-term economic and environmental impacts, which imposes further challenges on city planners and policymakers to guide and support adoption choices, beneficial to individuals and society.

Objective: The objective of this case study is to examine the expansion of district

heating in Lyngby municipality, through a social science and humanities lens, and to develop and compare appropriate solutions, to guarantee carbon-neutral heat to all in the municipality.

Expected benefits. Lyngby hopes that the studies will help identify strategies for achieving the municipality's goal of 98% district heating coverage by 2030. The experiences from this development can be deployed in other cities and communities.

Description of Case Study

The goal of the Heating Plan 2022-2030 (Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality, 2022) is that 98% of households in Lyngby-Taarbæk have been offered district heating by the end of 2030. The plan, therefore, involves a crucial shift from primarily gas to almost exclusively district heating - in no more than eight years. An ambitious project that requires cooperation and will shape the cityscape for years to come.

Today, 59% of the buildings in Lyngby-Taarbæk municipality are supplied by natural gas. However, since 2013, LTM has started an extensive district heating expansion plan to phase out the gas supply for heating in the city. The plan targets priority areas where the building stock is dense, and heat consumption is high. Recently, a sensitivity study of the conversion to DH included the recent price hikes in raw materials and labour, showing societal-, business- and end-user economic viability in district

heating expansion to 70% of the municipality's heating needs by 2030. Regardless of the share of DH, the remaining share of the buildings not connected to district heating will need to switch to alternatives – such as heat pumps or local heat networks. Finally, there still exists pockets of consumption showing limited connectivity potential to district heating and equipped with recent fossil fuel-based boilers. These may have incentives to extend their operation beyond 2030.

The heat plan's (Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality, 2022) map, figure 36, shows districts (blue) that are scheduled for conversion to DH. Areas outside DH supply (yellow and orange), are not socio-economically viable for district heating. Instead, these areas will be supplied by alternative heat sources.

Figure 36 - Heat Plan Map

The case study focuses on the deployment of the district heating network in the medium term. Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality is atypical in the sense that 27% of residents have MSc-level or above. This is the highest in Denmark. The municipality has noted that in terms of communicating complex challenges and projects, this is an advantage, as people tend to grasp complex planning issues

easily. This also requires well-prepared municipal authorities since residents are prone to challenge initiatives with in-depth questions and insights. Occasionally, residents even develop alternative solutions in self-established groups.

Case Study

Solution

Such a task (heat planning for a new area) is usually conducted by a consultancy in a process combining techno-economic analysis of the heat supply (e.g. modelling in tools such as the energyPRO software), GIS-analysis (to determine demands + network length) and some degree of stakeholder engagement (e.g. information meetings). The current case deviates somewhat from the typical district heating development, as the scope is solely focused on the stakeholder aspects. The process and methods LTM are explained in the following.

We leave the “classic parts” of heat planning and development (demand mapping and modelling) to the consultants. Instead, we focus on social acceptance and energy poverty. We analyse these topics through the engagement of

stakeholders as explained in the following.

Data collection is conducted as follows. Literature is reviewed for similar cases (e.g. heating area developments or studies of the same geography as the current case). Furthermore, grey literature is explored, as this field may contain aspects not yet found in scientific literature.

Building on the literature review, a workshop is conducted. The workshop includes the municipal energy planner and the city’s Sustainability Lab. The municipality brings experience in heat planning (e.g. the types of consumption, the inhabitants, and the available capital). The Sustainability Lab brings insights into how local solution providers can enable the transition, thereby mapping the project’s local commercial potential.

The outcome of the review and workshop is a mapping of what local stakeholders need and what they can offer regarding the new heat supply. It will be explored whether the characteristics can be classified

according to social science and humanities methods (energy acceptance/justice/poverty), and subsequently how to address these in developing the solution.

The solution will target the development of end-user engagement models (e.g. communication, co-ownership or representation), business models (e.g. profit/non-profit) and finance solutions (e.g. arrangements with local banks).

Results and Discussion

The objective of this case study is to examine the expansion of district heating in Lyngby municipality, through a social science and humanities lens, to develop and compare appropriate solutions, and to guarantee carbon-neutral heat to all in the municipality. The following results are based on dialogue and a workshop with LTM. Solutions are based on the workshop, and supplemented with literature on the subject.

Needs and solutions

Stronger communication

- **Need:** The municipality sees a major potential in improved stakeholder engagement through communication on energy planning and transition. Particularly, in helping the utilities improve communication to enable a better understanding of strategies and plans among residents.

- **Solution:** Typically, there is limited engagement from DH end-users when they have been connected and the supply is stable and affordable (Janssen et al., 2023). But in the period of deployment, there is an increased need for visibility, local engagement and establishment of trust in DH (Verstraten et al., 2021). The municipality has had successful stakeholder meetings, both physically and online, informing about their energy transition initiatives. These meetings have been over-subscribed and with large public interest. The municipality ascribes part of the success to the professional production of the online event. Here, a studio was rented, and a professional production crew and equipment elevated the event from regular “talking head and slides” to a more television-like experience. Continuing the path of

physical and virtual meetings is sensible, as this has already proven successful. To address the need for more engagement between the utilities, LTM and end-users, LTM can facilitate brief, but frequent updates from the utility. Furthermore, everyday online presence is important (especially social media) (Verstraten et al., 2021). As this is a significant task, and since the utility is typically fully engaged with the transition process, it may be beneficial to delegate it to service providers

Neighbouring district heating

- **Need:** The municipality sees benefit in collaboration with neighbouring municipalities, e.g. Rudersdal. Heat supply should not be constrained by municipal borders, meaning that Lyngby’s DH company can supply nearby municipalities’ areas that are hard to reach for neighbouring DH utilities. Vice versa, Lyngby’s hard-to-reach areas for DH, may be close to neighbouring DH networks. These potentials need mapping.

- **Solution:** LTM can facilitate contact with neighbouring municipalities and their utilities (Verstraten et al., 2021). In the present case, there is already a well-established collaboration on energy- and heat planning in the Danish capital region, so dialogue can happen bilaterally or through the network. LTM can also contribute to driving the process and brokering an agreement, as utilities may be averse to expanding into new areas, particularly those with lower heat density.

Diversified district heating

- **Need:** More excess heat from more sources. This is necessary to transition from the current fossil-based shares of DH supply.
- **Solution:** Two steps are necessary. Firstly, a mapping of potential sources. Second, engaging and contracting with the suppliers. LTM and the utility have initiated the mapping with the recent heat plan.

Sources in neighbouring municipalities should also be surveyed, to ensure the use of low-hanging fruits. Supply of excess heat is typically challenged by three issues (Sieverts et al., 2022): 1) Limited awareness among suppliers, as this is a secondary product to their primary product. 2) Perceived administrative complexity in establishing agreements. 3) Low profit motive for the supplier, as the DH utility must use the least cost heat source. This limits the payable amount to the supplier. Regarding 1, LTM and Lyngby's Sustainability Lab can map potential suppliers and organise events that raise awareness and opportunities. The utility and LTM, in collaboration with other utilities and municipalities, may benefit from a streamlined approach. Here, the contracts can be standardised to fast-track the agreements.

Certainty in heat supply

- **Need:** By 2022, the municipality informed all residents of the prospects of DH supply. This deployment is a major infrastructure project, so it cannot happen all at once. Instead, the deployment is spread over the period until 2028. According to the municipality, residents who can get DH within a brief period are inclined to do so. Those with DH scheduled multiple years into the future may be more inclined to find alternative solutions. This can, in turn, undermine the business case for DH deployment in these areas, leading to a societally sub-optimal solution. Certainty is a double challenge, as the DH utility needs a certain number of subscribers to have a positive business case. For end-users, certainty also concerns the energy (typically gas) prices until they can get DH.
- **Solution:** The utility offers a non-profit service agreement to gas customers, enabling maintenance and replacement of the gas boiler until the DH arrives. This addresses technological risk for the end-user. Price risk remains, as the customer is still responsible for the gas purchase. To address the latter, the utilities can explore the legal options for providing heat as a service i.e. providing heat regardless of technology. This includes providing long-term gas contracts for customers, in exchange for a legally binding obligation to connect to DH. or to provide and service a supplementary air-air heat pump that can reduce gas consumption and thereby reduce gas price risk. Reducing risk on the DH company's side includes the provision of a "cold plug", offering end-users with e.g. new heat pump or gas boiler a distribution pipe. At the end

of life (typically 15 years) of the current technology, the end-user can be connected to DH.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality, its inhabitants and the district heating supply utility stand in front of a large task. They

must collectively find solutions to transition the largely gas-based heating system to district heating. In this study, we have mapped the needs of the stakeholders, and we provide corresponding solutions based on the stakeholder dialogue, existing practice and literature.

Needs include stronger communication among stakeholders, better integration with neighbouring district heating systems, diversified and decarbonised heat supply and long-term certainty in heat supply among end-users and district heating utility. Clear and persistent communication is an overlapping solution for all these, with the municipality as a well-placed liaison. Further, attractive business models need to be developed for the supply of district heating from neighbouring utilities, provision of excess, carbon-free heat to the district heating system, for the end-users to connect to district heating and for the district heating utility to responsibly deploy district heating according to the municipal plan.

These are substantial tasks that require broad collaboration and coordination from the municipality. Large infrastructure projects like this take time, so it is necessary to simultaneously initiate local action – i.e. the deployment and communication efforts within the municipality – and the municipality-external dialogues on heat supply and development of business models. The latter is relevant for municipalities and utilities across the country, so a collaborative effort is relevant. But it should not become an excuse for inaction. Conversely, the planning department in Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality must receive strong political and budgetary support, for the politically enacted plans to become pipes in the ground and not a pipe dream.

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